

TETRALOGY OF FALLOT: ASSOCIATION WITH OTHER CONGENITAL HEART DISEASES AND CHROMOSOMAL ABNORMALITIES

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Resume. By some literature in the Republic of Belarus the ratio of congenital malformations of the heart to other congenital defects is 30%, including a congenital defect such as Tetralogy of Fallot, that is about 7-10%. The research describes beginning of congenital heart defect depending on mother's age, health condition and genetic diseases.

Keywords: a Tetralogy of Fallot, a congenital heart malformation, congenital malformations, chromosomal diseases

Relevance. The relevance of the topic is due to the fact that currently a large number of children are born with various heart defects, including Fallot's Notebook. In most cases, this defect undergoes successful surgical treatment, which is performed in several stages. [1]

Purpose: To study the main causes of the formation of the Tetrad of Fallot.

Tasks: 1. To establish the connection of the Tetrad of Fallot with other congenital malformations, chromosomal diseases. 2. To identify the dependence of the formation of a defect on the state of health and age of the mother. 3. Compare the data of the studied literature with the results of the conducted research.

Material and methods. In the course of the work, the genetic maps of pregnant women in Minsk for 2009-2011, examined on the basis of the RNPC, were evaluated "Mother and child", diagnosed with Tetrad Fallot at various stages of fetal development.

The results and their discussion. The study showed that the defect is more often formed during pregnancy in patients over 35 years of age: in pregnant women from 20 to 25 years-in 27% of cases, from 26 to 30 years-19%, from 31 to 35 years-12%, from 36 years and older 42%.

It was found that in the studied cases TF is most often represented by a combination of the following heart defects: • ventricular septal defect-65% of all studied cases • pulmonary artery stenosis-50% • aortic dextraposition-35% • pulmonary trunk stenosis-15%, which corresponds to the literature data. [1] TF was found to be associated with congenital malformations of the following systems: • musculoskeletal system-27% of all studied cases (hypoplasia of the

bones of the facial skull, polydactyly, clubfoot) • defects of the digestive tract- 12% • kidney defects - 1%. A study of the relationship of TF with chromosomal abnormalities found an association of TF with Down syndrome in 39% of cases, with Edwards syndrome in 6% of cases, and not a single case of an association of a defect with Patau syndrome, although according to the literature the latter is often found. [2] A study of the association of TF with other congenital heart defects found that in 19% of cases there is a combination of TF with double discharge of the main vessels. In an equal number of cases (an average of 6%), TF was associated with the following heart defects: hypoplasia of the valvular ring of the heart, absence of the Botall duct, violation of the continuous connection of the interventricular septum with the ascending part of the aorta, the rider's aorta, pulmonary artery atresia, persistent superior vena cava.

Most often, TF is definitively diagnosed at 19-22 weeks of gestation with routine ultrasound. Thus, the dependence of the formation of the defect on the sex of the fetus was revealed: in 57% of cases TF was observed in male fetuses, in 43% of cases female.

In the studied cases, there is no relationship between the professions of pregnant women and the development of malformation in fetuses. None of the patients had malformations or any acquired heart diseases, and the only woman examined had a viral disease in the first trimester (fever up to 38 °C).

Conclusions: 1 The formation of the Fallot Tetrad is determined by the age of the mother: it is most often formed during pregnancy in patients older than 35 years. 2 TF is represented by a combination of the following heart defects: ventricular septal defect, pulmonary artery stenosis, aortic dextraposition, pulmonary trunk stenosis. 3 This CHD is not isolated, it is associated with: - other heart defects that are not included in the usual combination of heart defects in TF; - various abnormalities of the development of the musculoskeletal system, digestive tract and kidney defects; - chromosomal diseases: most often with Down syndrome, less often with Edwards syndrome. 4 T F is more often formed in male fetuses. 5 TF can be diagnosed at 19-22 weeks of gestation with a second ultrasound. 6 Pregnancies ended in childbirth in 50% of cases. Thus, the conducted research indicates that the pathogenesis of DF may be based on a number of molecular genetic disorders of various origins, which cause multiple abnormalities in the development of vital body systems.

References:

1. <https://www.heart.org/en/health-topics/congenital-heart-defects/about-congenital-heart-defects/tetralogy-of-fallot>.
2. <https://www.ahajournals.org/doi/10.1161/CIRCRESAHA.118.314520>

3. Bernstein D. Cyanotic congenital heart disease: evaluation of the critically ill neonate with cyanosis and respiratory distress. In: Kliegman RM, St. Geme JW, Blum NJ, Shah SS, Tasker RC, MBBS, Wilson KM, eds. Nelson Textbook of Pediatrics. 21st ed. Philadelphia, PA: Elsevier; 2020:chap 456.
4. Valente AM, Dorfman AL, Babu-Narayan SV, Kreiger EV. Congenital heart disease in the adolescent and adult. In: Libby P, Bonow RO, Mann DL, Tomaselli GF, Bhatt DL, Solomon SD eds. Braunwald's Heart Disease: A Textbook of Cardiovascular Medicine. 12th ed. Philadelphia, PA: Elsevier; 2022:chap 82.
5. Well A, Fraser CD. Congenital heart disease. In: Townsend CM Jr, Beauchamp RD, Evers BM, Mattox KL, eds. Sabiston Textbook of Surgery. 21st ed. St Louis, MO: Elsevier; 2022:chap 59.